

The Influence of Allostatic Load and *APOE* on Cortical Thinning

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Abstract

Objectives

Although short-term stress is beneficial for increasing focus and performance, prolonged stress is associated with negative outcomes on brain structure and function. Research suggests that allostatic load, a measure of the cumulative burden of stress, has the ability to diminish the thickness of the cerebral cortex, resulting in increased psychopathology. Several factors may influence this relationship, such as the apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) gene, which has been implicated in cognitive decline and Alzheimer's disease. Longitudinal studies are needed, however, to understand these long-term effects in late adulthood. Here, we hypothesized that *APOE* moderates the relationship between allostatic load and cortical thinning.

Methods

Participants ($N = 51$; $M_{\text{age}} = 64.80 \pm 7.09$; 61% female; 84% White) were selected from the Notre Dame Study of Health & Well-being, a 15-year longitudinal study, which constitutes the Science of Wellness sample (NDHWB-SoW). Allostatic load and *APOE* status were calculated from blood samples and in-person health assessments, and cortical thinning was assessed using MRI.

Results

We found no direct effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning, but this link and the interaction were significant with *APOE* added into the model, exhibiting a significant moderation effect.

Discussion

This work is critical to understanding the long-term burden of stress and heredity on brain structure and may inform interventions aimed at preserving brain health in mid to late adulthood by addressing chronic stress as a significant risk factor, especially for those who have *APOE* $\epsilon 4$.

Keywords: cerebral cortex; MRI; stress; genetics

Introduction

Stress is an unavoidable part of life. Although stress is beneficial in the short-term for increasing focus and performance, prolonged stress can result in a cumulation of physiological burden on the body, known as allostatic load (McEwen & Stellar, 1993). Research also suggests that allostatic load can diminish the thickness of the cerebral cortex, a part of the brain essential for higher-level processing, which is associated with adverse functioning and increased psychopathology, including changes in cognitive functioning (Chiappelli et al., 2017; Ottino-González et al., 2017; van Haren et al., 2011). One factor that may influence the allostatic load-cortical thinning relationship is the apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) gene, such that e4 carriers have been shown to exhibit greater cortical thinning (Espeseth et al., 2008). Further longitudinal studies are needed, however, to understand the long-term cumulative effects of allostatic load and *APOE* status on cortical thinning in late adulthood.

Allostatic Load and Cortical Thinning

The allostatic load model, proposed by McEwen and Stellar (1993), outlines the detrimental effect of chronic stress on the body. *Allostatic load* is the downstream effect of stress, which “should signal [the] pending onset of diverse kinds of disability and disease” (Schulkin, 2004, p. 113). For example, allostatic load impairs metabolic, inflammatory, and cardiac functioning, all of which can have negative effects on cognitive performance (Epel et al., 2018; Schulkin, 2004). Prolonged stress arousal can also negatively influence brain plasticity in areas such as the hippocampus, amygdala, and the prefrontal cortex (McEwen & Gianaros, 2011). Allostatic load has been shown to have consistently strong predictive value of mortality and decline in physical functioning in both short (e.g., 2.5 years), and long longitudinal studies (7.5 years; Seeman et al., 2001).

One negative consequence of stress on the brain is cortical thinning. A reduction in cerebral cortex thickness is known as *cortical thinning*, a healthy phenomenon during adolescence that is suggested to improve neuropsychological performance (Squeglia et al., 2013). In later life, widespread cortical thinning can occur in healthy aging as well (Fjell et al., 2009; Thambisetty et al., 2010), but substantial cortical thinning is often associated with deleterious outcomes, such as mild cognitive impairment and ultimately Alzheimer's disease (Singh et al., 2006). Furthermore, the pathological patterns of cortical thinning have a distinct spatial organization in the temporal lobe, parietal lobe, and prefrontal areas, which differentiates them from spatial patterns of cortical thinning in healthy aging (Kang et al., 2019).

Research suggests that allostatic load increases cortical thinning because of chronic biological dysregulation and inflammation, in both cognitively normal individuals (Zsoldos et al., 2018) and in those with diseases such as schizophrenia and obesity (Chiappelli et al., 2017; Ottino-González et al., 2017; van Haren et al., 2011). In normal individuals, one key area that allostatic load structurally affects is the prefrontal cortex, reflecting how chronic stress impairs cognitive flexibility and decision making (McEwen & Gianaros, 2011). Recent research suggests that individuals with a history of psychiatric disease exhibit reduced gray matter volume in the prefrontal cortex as a result of stressful life events (Palpatzis et al., 2024), providing further evidence for the association between long-term stress and cortical thinning. Here, we focus on the allostatic load-cortical thinning relationship in a community sample of older adults.

Apolipoprotein E (*APOE*)

One factor that may influence the allostatic load-cortical thinning relationship is apolipoprotein E (*APOE*). *APOE* is a gene involved in cholesterol transport and is predictive of changes in cognitive health (Corbo & Scacchi, 1999). There are 3 alleles associated with *APOE*:

e2 is related to longevity and good health; e3 has a neutral effect on health; and e4 has the potential to cause deleterious outcomes (Corbo & Scacchi, 1999). Notably, the e4 allele is associated with cortical thinning, such that *APOE* e4 carriers have greater cortical thinning than *APOE* e3 or *APOE* e2 carriers (Espeseth et al., 2008). Research suggests that an interaction effect can be seen, such that the salivary cortisol**APOE* e4 interaction results in a greater detrimental effect on memory compared to individuals who do not have at least one e4 allele (Peavy et al., 2007). Beyond affecting behavioral markers of memory, the e4 allele interaction with physiological measures of stress (allostatic load) across the lifespan has not been studied in relation to cortical thinning, to the best of our knowledge. Further studies are needed to understand the long-term effects of allostatic load and *APOE* on cortical thinning in late adulthood.

The Present Study

Here, we used a moderation model to test the influence of *APOE* status on the relationship between allostatic load and cortical thinning. We used longitudinal data from the Notre Dame Study of Health & Well-being (NDHWB; see Bergeman et al., 2021 for details), which aimed to investigate factors leading to healthy aging. We hypothesized that allostatic load would predict cortical thinning, and *APOE* would moderate this association. Specifically, *APOE* e4 individuals would have stronger relationships between allostatic load and cortical thinning, whereas those without *APOE* e4 would have less strong relationships between allostatic load and cortical thinning.

Methods

Participants

Participants were selected from the NDHWB (Bergeman et al., 2021) to create the Science of Wellness (SoW) project. NDHWB-SoW participants (n = 51) ranged between the ages of 40 to 87 (mean age = 64.8, 61% female, 84% White), and most attained at least a high school degree (98%) and had an annual income of at least \$25,000 (84%). Selection criteria included active participation in the NDHWB, native English proficiency, and normal or corrected-to-normal vision and hearing. All participants confirmed a lack of substance abuse, current psychological or neurological issues, seizures, stroke, neuroactive medication intake, severe head injury, concussion within the past three months, memory loss, uncontrolled hypertension or diabetes, metal in their brain, history of stroke, and any COVID-19 risk factors.

Measures and Materials

Allostatic Load

Allostatic load was assessed at Wave 11 (occurring between 2017-2019) using blood assessments, saliva measures, and anthropomorphic assessments in accordance with previous work (Seeman et al., 2010). The blood assessment was performed by LabCorp and included high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), the ratio of HDL to LDL, triglycerides, hemoglobin A1c, homocysteine, c-reactive protein, interleukin 6, and tumor necrosis factor- α . Systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and resting heart rate were recorded as anthropometric measures, all of which were taken as the average of two measurements five minutes apart. Other anthropometric indicators included waist to hip ratio and body mass index. Average evening salivary cortisol levels were measured across 7 days and sent to Salimetrics for processing.

Clinical cut off levels for the blood assessment (Labcorp, 2024) and top quartile measures for anthropomorphic and salivary assessments were used. Calculation of allostatic load

was completed in accordance with guidelines from previous work (Seeman et al., 2010). To score allostatic load, each system that showed dysregulation received a “1”, for a possible total of 7 such that higher scores indicate greater allostatic load (cardiovascular—lipid, cardiovascular—blood pressure, cardiovascular—homocysteine, metabolic, endocrine, inflammatory, and immune). Regarding the blood pressure, lipid, and metabolic systems, individuals were classified as dysregulated if they were on medication for triglycerides, high blood pressure, diabetes, or cholesterol. Scores were normally distributed ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 1.27$, $Skew = 0.07$, $Kurtosis = -0.17$) and ranged from 0 to 6.

APOE status

Participants were genotyped for *APOE* status using blood analysis at Wave 14 performed by LabCorp. The three polymorphisms of the *APOE* allele include *APOE* e2, *APOE* e3, and *APOE* e4. Participants were divided into three groups based on available genotypes: e2 (e2/e3), e3 (e3/e3), and e4 (e3/e4 and e4/e4).

Data Acquisition

Structural images were acquired using a 1.5T GE SIGNA Voyager equipped with a 32-channel head coil using a 3D T1-weighted BRAVO sequence (in-plane dimensions = 256 x 256; in-plane resolution = 1mm X 1mm; 168 slices; slice thickness = 1.24 mm; TE = 3.2 ms; TR = 7.9 ms).

Cortical Thinning

Cortical thinning was assessed using structural MRI at Wave 12. Cortical thickness was derived from each participant's T1-weighted image using Freesurfer's (v6.0) semi-automatic processing pipeline (<http://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/fswiki>; Fischl & Dale, 2000). First, each 3-dimensional T1 volume underwent skull-stripping and intensity normalization. Next, the T1

volume was reconstructed as an inflated 2-dimensional surface so that pial surfaces and white matter could be more easily identified for the left and right hemisphere. Cortical thickness could then be estimated using these surface estimates.

After completion of this first step, white matter and pial surfaces were visually inspected by a trained research assistant. The automated analysis generally succeeded in identifying white and gray matter boundaries, however, some brain regions required further manual edits. Tissue classification errors were corrected by editing the white matter and brain masks returned by the first iteration through the Freesurfer pipeline. In addition, ‘control points’ were added to voxels on, or close to, what were determined to be white matter tracts that had been excluded by the automated analysis. Manual edits were repeated as necessary.

Cortical thickness was measured as the distance from the gray/white matter boundary to the pial surface on a vertex-by-vertex basis across the entire cortical mantle of each hemisphere. Mean whole-brain cortical thickness was calculated by averaging cortical thickness values generated for the two hemispheres excluding subcortical structures, white matter regions, cerebellum and brainstem.

Statistical Analyses

These data were analyzed using R Studio (version 4.2.2). We examined the (1) direct effect of allostatic load and *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ on cortical thinning and (2) moderating effect of *APOE* on this relationship. All potential covariates (age, sex, race, income, and mean years of education) were examined via ANOVA. Pearson correlations were run for all continuous variables, and point-biserial correlations were used for categorical variables (i.e., sex and race).

Results

Preliminary Analyses

Race was positively correlated with allostatic load ($r = .30, p < .05$), such that White individuals were more likely to have higher allostatic load. There were no direct effects of income, $F(6,50) = .63, p > .05$, race, $F(2,50) = .38, p > .05$, sex, $F(1,50) = .68, p > .05$, or education, $F(6,50) = .83, p > .05$, on cortical thinning. Although there was a positive direct effect of age on cortical thinning, $F(1,50) = 7.96, p < .01$, it should be noted that age was not included in the moderation analysis to maximize power given that age did not correlate with allostatic load or *APOE*.

Primary Analyses

In the main effects model, there was no significant effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning ($\beta = -.01, SE = .01, p > .05, 95\% \text{ CI of B } [-.03, .01]$). However, when *APOE* was added as a moderator, the direct effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning was marginally significant ($\beta = .13, SE = .06, p = .0507, 95\% \text{ CI of B } [-.0004, .25]$). This model showed a significant moderation effect ($\beta = -.04, SE = .02, p < .05, 95\% \text{ CI of B } [-.08, -.003]$), which accounted for 13.69% of the variance. A Johnson-Neyman plot shows this interaction (Figure 1). Only e4 significantly moderated the allostatic load - cortical thinning relationships, such that for those who have at least one e4 allele, higher allostatic load was associated with greater cortical thinning ($\beta = -.03, SE = .01, p < .05$). The e3 ($\beta = -.01, SE = .01, p > .05$) and e2 ($\beta = .01, SE = .01, p > .05$) alleles were not significant.

Discussion

The goal of this study was to investigate the relationship between allostatic load, *APOE*, and cortical thinning in older adults. We hypothesized that allostatic load would predict cortical thinning, and *APOE* would moderate this relationship. The results of this research provide

supporting evidence that the *APOE* e4 allele strengthens the effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning in older adults.

Inconsistent with previous literature (Chiappelli et al., 2017; Ottino-González et al., 2017; Zsoldos et al., 2018), we did not find a direct effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning, possibly because there is a notable inconsistency in defining “allostatic load” throughout the literature. For example, over 50 different biomarkers have been recorded through various meta-analyses to be included in the definition of allostatic load (McCrory et al., 2023). Another reason our study may have yielded a nonsignificant result is because interactions with other covarying factors, such as genetic polymorphisms, mask this effect. It is also possible that the effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning is small, such that our sample size was not large enough to detect a smaller effect.

Regarding the significant moderation effect, the finding that the *APOE* e4 allele strengthens the effect of allostatic load on cortical thinning is consistent with our hypothesis and previous literature. Corbo and Scacchi (1999) found that the e4 allele increases risk for many negative psychological and physiological effects, and Espeseth and colleagues (2008) extended this finding to report that e4 carriers have greater cortical thinning. Here, we report that the only significant allele is e4, which is indeed associated with higher allostatic load (Arbeev et al., 2023) and increased cortical thinning (Espeseth et al., 2008), the latter of which is a negative outcome associated with psychopathology (Kang et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2006). Furthermore, Peavy and colleagues (2007) describe a significant interaction between stress and *APOE* e4 on memory. Our findings extend this work by using allostatic load as the cumulative burden of stress on the body, rather than only using a behavioral indicator of stress as with previous research (Peavy et al., 2007).

There are a handful of limitations to this study, however. Our sample was relatively small ($N = 51$) and there are limits to generalizability, given that participants were predominantly white and from the northern Indiana area. A more ethnically and geographically diverse sample might show a more distinct relationship. Additionally, static MRI was used to collect data rather than dynamic MRI, although only static MRI is necessary to calculate cortical thickness. Allostatic load also exhibited restricted range such that most participants had a score between 0-3 (range = 0-6), indicating a limitation of range. Future work should address these limitations by using dynamic MRI and a larger, more diverse sample to replicate our finding that *APOE* e4 moderates the allostatic load-cortical thinning association in older adults.

The present study has real-world implications. This work may inform targeted interventions to preserve brain health in mid to late adulthood by addressing chronic stress as a significant risk factor. In practice, stress management should be promoted early in life by doctors and continued throughout the lifespan. This can further be implemented in the workplace by fostering environments that support mental well-being, such as flexible work arrangements (Chandola et al., 2019). Further, our work shows that allostatic load and *APOE* status (specifically e4) show promise to be used as a non-invasive, low-cost biomarker for brain health in mid to late adulthood. In confluence, these interactive effects inform the potential progression of cortical thinning, a precursor to Alzheimer's disease. Overall, this work highlights the detrimental effect that genetics and physiological stress have on the aging brain.

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Figure 1

Johnson-Neyman plot for moderation effect of APOE on the link between allostatic load and cortical thinning

Note. Each line represents a different *APOE* allele (e4, e3, and e2), but only the e4 line was shown to be significant.